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FOCUS-5 Learning Report: Communicating Federation Concepts

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UK Research
and Innovation

Health Data Research UK

ADRUK

Part of the
North West
SECURE DATA
ENVIRONMENT

Acronyms and Abbreviations

DARE UK	Data and Analytics Research Environments UK
EM	East Midlands
EoE	East of England
FedRes CIG	Federated Research Community Interest Group
FOCUS-5	Federating Operations and Collaborations Using the Five Safes
NENC	North East and North Cumbria
PANORAMA	Pan-North Data Research Advancements for Multi-Domain Access and Analysis
PPIE	Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement
RO	Research objects
SACRO	Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs
SATRE	Standardised Architecture for Trusted Research Environments
SDE	Secure Data Environment
TRE	Trusted Research Environment
VISTA	Viable Implementation of SATRE, SACRO and Tools for AI
YH	Yorkshire and Humber

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1. Executive Summary

Communicating federation concepts in data research

This report shares learning from work linked to DARE UK, DataSHIELD, FOCUS 5, NHS Secure Data Environments and public engagement in Lancashire and South Cumbria. The original aim was to create clearer public information about federation, federated data and federated analytics. The work found that the main problem was not simply a lack of resources. The bigger issue was that different people were using the same words in different ways. This included technical teams, researchers, governance staff, public engagement teams, policy colleagues and members of the public.

In simple terms, federation is about finding ways for data, systems or organisations to work together without always moving all the data into one central place. This matters because data, such as that about people's health is sensitive. People often support data being used for public benefit, but they also want clear answers about who can access it, how it is protected, whether it is copied or moved, and how the benefits will come back to patients and communities.

The report shows that early messages about Secure Data Environments and Trusted Research Environments often suggested that data would be accessed safely without routine sharing. However, the word routine can be understood in different ways. This creates a risk that the public may feel one thing was promised and another thing is happening later. Figures 1 and 2 show how this concern emerged from early project assumptions and from national messaging about moving away from routine sharing of health data.

Figure 3 adds an important point. It presents federated analytics as a way to analyse data across places while reducing the need to centralise data. This can help answer public concerns about cyber attacks, large central targets and data being moved around. The report notes that NHS public attitude work found high concern about cyber attacks on health data, and that later cyber incidents may have strengthened public worries about data security.

The work was developed through a series of public and professional discussions during 2025 and early 2026. These included DARE UK Early Adopter meetings, a national public webinar, Lancashire and South Cumbria Public Advisory Group workshops, work on explainer videos, a public forum on output checking, collaboration with NHS SDE public engagement leads, a workshop with a federated analytics expert, and work with the DARE UK Federated Research Community Interest Group. Each stage showed that people were not only asking for simpler words. They were asking for clearer shared meaning behind the words.

A key learning was that public resources cannot be created well if professionals have not first agreed what the main terms mean. The report explains that federation sits between technical design, governance, policy, communications and public engagement. Each group needs something slightly different from the language. Technical teams need precise terms. Public engagement teams need concepts and terms that stay consistent when explained in plain English. Governance teams need clarity about risk, assurance and accountability. When these needs are not discussed openly, meanings can drift and trust can be damaged.

The figures in the report show how the work moved from simple explanations towards shared language tools. Figure 5 shows a draft language tree map. This was created because a simple glossary was not enough to show how terms relate to each other. Figure 6 shows a summary strategy developed after a joint meeting between the DARE UK federation group and Northern NHS SDE public engagement professionals. Figures 7 and 8 show the prototype Federation Atlas, which presents terms in both a graph view and a table view so people can explore how ideas connect.

The Federation Atlas is an important output because it responds to a real need from both technical and public engagement communities. It aims to support a shared, searchable and visible way to explain terms linked to federation. It also recognises that definitions should not be owned by one organisation alone. They need to be maintained across the wider sector, with public and professional input.

The report also explains why early resource creation proved premature. FOCUS 5 tried to develop videos, storyboards and infographics. These were useful because they exposed where confusion existed. However, they also showed that polished public materials can move faster than professional agreements. This is risky when assumptions are still changing, especially around whether data stays under local control, whether it is shared across boundaries, or whether some places are moving towards pooled data.

The appendix offers two helpful analogies. The library analogy explains federation as a network of libraries. Each library keeps its books on its own shelves, but shared catalogues and rules allow approved questions to be answered across libraries. The librarian represents the controlled software or trusted process. The final answer is checked before it is released. The restaurant analogy explains a Secure Data Environment as a professional kitchen, where approved ingredients, trained staff, clear recipes, hygiene rules, final checks and serving the meal all represent parts of safe data use, analysis and public benefit.

The overall message is that good communication is part of the infrastructure. It is not an add-on at the end. If different parts of the system describe federation differently, people may lose confidence, even if the technical work is strong. The public can understand complex ideas when they are explained honestly, with examples and limits. The issue is not public ability. The issue is whether the system can speak clearly and consistently.

The report recommends a staged approach. First, continue language work across professional groups before scaling up public campaigns. Second, separate stable principles from current delivery choices and operational limits. Third, create a central source of agreed information that can be updated and used across organisations. Fourth, produce layered resources, from concise plain English summaries to more detailed explanations for those who want them. Fifth, recreate public animations that use stories to build understanding, confidence and trust in secure, data-driven research.

In conclusion, the work shows that federation is not only a technical challenge. It is also a language, trust and governance challenge. Better public communication depends on clearer professional agreements first. The next stage should focus on shared principles, agreed definitions, worked examples, and publicly tested resources that explain what is happening, what is not happening, what is still changing, and how people and their data are protected.

2. Purpose and context

This report summarises key learning from work across Data and Analytics Research Environments UK (DARE UK)-linked activity, DataSHIELD collaboration, and Lancashire and South Cumbria public engagement on federated analytics. The original aim was to create clearer public-facing resources on federation, federated data, and federated analytics. In trying to do so, it became apparent that resource production was not the main bottleneck. The larger issue was that the language itself was still being interpreted differently across different professional and public communities. Communication work, therefore, became an exercise in identifying where shared understanding did and did not yet exist. This resulted in broadening co-creation requirements to include professionals across organisations, career stages and branches of practice (technical, information governance, public engagement, researchers, policy makers). Our lived experience as professionals, but also high-authority UK policy and implementation literature, suggests that digital and data change is not routinely designed with sufficient involvement from all parts of the workforce; responsibility can fall to a small technical core, frontline staff may lack confidence, specialist analyst communities can become dispersed and isolated, and hierarchy can constrain whose voices are heard. Given that effective implementation depends on clinical, operational, analytical, and technical staff changing how they work, excluding these groups risks weaker design, poorer adoption, and reduced sustainment. [1, 2, 3]

3. Timeline and evolution of concerns through public and professional engagement

3.1. February 2025: FOCUS-5 kick-off meeting

Figure 1 was part of a Federating Operations and Collaborations Using the Five Safes (FOCUS-5) internal team Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) presentation.

<p>Problems to solve</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Current public resources are still significantly technical<ul style="list-style-type: none">◦ Written descriptions not sufficient to support more widespread understanding --> Videos, infographics, SDE/Five safes context• Federation a critical aspect of delivering a “Data access” model

Figure 1 – Extract from internal team presentation at start of the project

This presentation was written with the belief and assumptions that secure data environments/trusted research environments (SDEs/TREs) and “federation” meant moving away from data sharing across regional boundaries, as that had been the message in prior years as a local and regional NHS SDE PPIE lead, evidenced by the Data Saves Lives report stating “this will put an end to routine sharing” (figure 2). [4] The key modifier here is the word “routine”, as this is in and of itself something that can be interpreted very differently by different people. This could risk being seen as saying or promising one thing and then doing another. A shift in data access and sharing practices and policies needs to be managed expertly, and the guardrails need to be transparently defined and not wander in meaning.

Secure data environments

[Secure data environments](#) – a subset of which are known as [trusted research environments](#) – are a big step forward in how data can be accessed securely in a virtual setting. Analysis takes place within a secure online platform rather than data being shared and distributed.

In secure data environments, access to data is granted to authorised researchers in a controlled and recorded manner. This will put an end to the routine sharing and distribution of healthcare data for research purposes. Users' interactions with the data will be recorded and monitored, and the information they can extract will be assessed and with personal identifiers removed. As no data that can be linked to an individual leaves the server, and all access to the data and analysis is monitored, we will greatly reduce the risk of data breaches or other misuse.

We will be mandating the use of secure data environments for NHS data, and engaging with the public, both to demonstrate their inherent benefits and to understand any remaining concerns.

Figure 2 – Data Saves Live Report Website Extract [4]

3.2.March 2025: DARE UK Early Adopters Meeting

This meeting brought together DARE UK Early Adopter projects, including their PPIE leads, enabling opportunities for networking, sharing of work package objectives, and identification of overlapping needs and challenges which would make fertile ground for collaboration and intentional convergence. [5] This space provided an overview of the aims of each project that became a stimulus for identifying opportunities to pool resources around areas that individual PPIE leads and teams may not be able to overcome without more network buy-in.

3.3.April 2025: FOCUS-5 presentation on the importance of a common language as part of the DARE UK TREvolution and Early Adopters National Public Webinar

This presentation was originally delivered in the context of the 5-Safes research object crates, which improve how data is handled, reported on, audited, etc., in a structured manner. We also included a description of “federated analytics”. Figure 3 presents this description, with an overview of the uses and benefits of a federated analytics approach, including DataSHIELD mechanisms. This perspective on federated analytics, however, is not necessarily shared more widely, particularly regarding data movement. This is a fundamental difference, both technically and

legally, and from a public perspective. Whilst definitions do change and evolve naturally with language, this requires consensus or true evolution of terminology and sub-terms, rather than passive drifting of definitions.

Figure 3 – Extract from FOCUS-5 presentation at the DARE UK TREvolution and Early Adopters National Public Webinar [6]

Full presentation <https://canva.link/re7j700v6lsuajb>, DARE UK slides: [link](#)

As noted in this slide, centralising data for research, is generally disliked due to security concerns. This is evidenced by UK public attitude surveys such as those conducted by the NHS in 2024, which showed up to 82% concern regarding cyber attacks on health data. [7]

Since then, further high-profile cyber incidents on health care infrastructure have occurred, such as the ransomware attack on NHS blood services, and most recently, incidents like the UK biobank data breach. [8] This may reinforce perceptions that data is vulnerable and that centralisation is an increased risk and a bigger target. Federated Data solutions that reduce the need to centralise data are therefore important in providing assurances and reducing real or perceived risks to support trust-building efforts with the public and data controllers.

3.4.May-June 2025: Lancashire South Cumbria Public Advisory Group Workshops

Two workshops were held with the Lancashire and South Cumbria Public Advisory Groups to explore concepts of federation. One of the early-developing resources is shown in Figure 4: a storyboard of data from its creation through its use in research in the context of federated analytics.

Figure 4 - Early storyboard of the data's journey before it is analysed using federated data solutions

3.5. August-September 2025: Federated analytics video drafting and co-production sessions

In these sessions, analogies for describing federated analytics were explored, including a library and a restaurant analogy. A draft video concept was also created. This attempted to make data more tangible and physical to support comprehension and visualisation.

3.5.1. Library Analogy for Federation

Federated analytics can be thought of as asking a question across a network of libraries. Each library holds its own collection of books, just as each organisation holds its own local data. Those books stay in their original library. They are not copied and shipped to a central place; instead, an approved question is sent through the library system. At each library, a trained librarian, following strict rules, checks only the relevant parts of the collection needed to answer that question. The librarian does not hand over the original books, they only return an approved summary or count. As the libraries use shared catalogues, classifications, and agreed-upon rules, the same question can be asked in multiple places in a consistent way. The summaries from each library can then be combined to build a bigger picture across the whole network, without any one library giving up control of its own records.

In this way, federated analytics allows knowledge to be built across many sites while keeping the underlying records where they belong. It is a model of asking locally, combining centrally, and protecting privacy throughout.

3.5.2. Restaurant Analogy for Trust Research Environments and Secure Data Environments

Other analogies had been discussed prior to FOCUS-5 with the Northwest SDE regions' PPIE groups regarding the Five Safes, also using communal spaces such as a restaurant. Reinforcing visualisation and tapping into the tacit appreciation of a supply chain and the delivery of trusted goods, such as the food we eat. In this case, health data research can be thought of like a trusted restaurant system. Raw ingredients come from approved suppliers, just as data comes from organisations that remain responsible for it. The ingredients are brought into a professional kitchen, which is like the SDE; a controlled space where only trained and authorised staff can work. Before any cooking begins, the recipe is agreed, just as a research project should have a clear approved question and method.

In the kitchen, ingredients are cleaned, prepared, combined, and handled carefully, just as data is curated, linked, and analysed. The research team, like a kitchen team led by a head chef, turns raw materials into something useful. But the dish cannot leave the kitchen unchecked. It goes through a final quality and safety review, just as research outputs are checked to ensure they do not reveal confidential information or make inappropriate claims.

Only then is the final product shared beyond the kitchen. In food, that is the meal reaching the diners. In health data research, that is, knowledge reaching clinicians, services, policymakers, and the public. The whole system is underpinned by standards, training, inspection, and accountability, so people can trust both the process and the benefit.

See Appendix 2 for a table of items that may be used to explore a story and analogy as a comic or video resource.

3.6. September 2025: Joint public forum on statistical disclosure control and automation

Northern NHS SDE PPIE and DARE UK Early Adopter PPIE leads ran a joint public forum on Statistical Disclosure controls and automation led by the DARE UK Viable Implementation of SATRE, SACRO and Tools for AI (VISTA) early adopter project. The public remarked on enjoying the joint forum as a way to connect with peers in this space and share learning and perspectives. This also promoted greater collaboration between PPIE leads and opportunities to develop shared perspectives on the challenges we face. Federation was raised as a potential future topic for greater collaboration across boundaries, given the need to automate output checking of intermediate research results to enable decentralised federated data and analytic approaches. It was recognised that the complexity of the subject matter would be a barrier to such conversations without better education and resources. This began to surface the low levels of confidence non-technical peers had in this subject, acting as a barrier to serving as translators to ultimately support public inclusion in a complex conversation and policy space.

3.7. October 2025 – Jan 2026: NHS SDE PPIE Collaboration

An informal coalition of NHS SDE PPIE regional leads and the FOCUS-5 PPIE lead continued to explore concerns about language and effective communication with the public. It became increasingly clear that this was also challenging professionals from other branches of practice, including governance and technical professionals too.

3.8. Jan 2026: Workshop with federated analytics subject matter expert (SME)

Regional organisations ran a joint workshop of communications and PPIE leads working across both the NHS SDE network (North East and North Cumbria, Yorkshire and Humber, East of England, East Midlands) and DARE UK early adopters (FOCUS-5, Pan-North Data Research Advancements for Multi-Domain Access and Analysis, VISTA) with a federated analytics expert of 10-years in this space building infrastructure and coding software that enables decentralised approaches. This workshop exposed significant anxieties about a shifting landscape and terminology, particularly the shifting goal posts around data sharing. This went against prior messaging, which another colleague independently raised. Here, the SME requested an exploration of terms in a more structured fashion, such as a definitions tree, as a starting point to help structure public- and professional-facing resources in a more logical and consistent manner. Early work is represented by Figure 5 (pg 10) which shows the evolution of placing terminology into a map with a split of definitions based on what is trying to be build or achieved inside and functions or methods that help achieve or deliver the objectives. This is represented by the green and purple colour keys, respectively. This began the thinking in terms of whys, hows, whats, and whos surrounding each item, which later influenced concept design for the Federation Atlas tool prototype.

3.9. Jan – March 2026: Joining the DARE UK Federated Research Community Interest Group

Members of the NHS SDE Regional PPIE and DARE UK Early Adopter professionals attended the [Federated Research Community Interest Group](#) (FedRes CIG) funded by DARE UK. Here, similar conversations had emerged regarding language consistency, and the tree map was presented. This resulted in suggestions for an interactive web version, with the European Parliament Research Service exemplar cited: <https://map.sciencemediahub.eu/5g#m=1/830.1924/453.23276> [9]. Following this meeting, a summary of the problem statement, context and additional work that needs to be sequenced to create clarity around language and then lead further PPIE was created (figure 6. Pg 11) .

“Federated Data” - Language and Solutions Tree Map

Definition: Federation is a structure where independent parts agree to work together under shared rules while keeping their own autonomy and control.

Figure 5 - Language Tree Map Draft Design in response to recognising that glossaries of terms in this space are not sufficient at demonstrating the relationships of terminology. Note that the definitions are placeholders and themselves require community-driven co-production.

A coalition to help better understand what “federation” and “federated data” really means

Problem Statement: The language around **federation** and **federating data** is confusing. Both are increasingly important concepts as an enabler of data research with robust privacy safeguards. The lack of clarity frustrates both internal communication between professionals who may interpret their meaning differently. As well as external communications to involve the public in policies that govern **federation**.

Background

- There are several glossaries and definitions relating to “**federation**”, “**federated data**”, “**federated analytics**”, “**data pooling**”, “**eyes-on/off analysis**”.
- There are limited accessible resources to help explain the concepts in written, visual, audio or blended formats. Prior attempts have failed.
- How the different concepts relate to each other is also poorly mapped out to help build an understand of what a truly **federated data research system** looks like.
- PPIE professionals across the system are starting to converge organically around some of these complex communication and engagement challenges. This has resulted in growing coalition of individuals from multiple organisations wanting to intentionally pool efforts to improve the quality and alignment of works produced.
- **To create resources and to involve the wider public there needs to be clarity around definitions and meaning first.**

You could call it “**federated engagement**”

Language Survey

- Seek feedback on current definitions and terms used across the UK Trusted Research Environment, NHS Secure Data Environment, Datamind to clarify consistencies and inconsistencies.
- Explore how definitions and interpretations may differ amongst different groups - governance, technical, data, policy

Consultation of professionals and public alike

Jan -
March
2026

Definition Tree Mapping Exercise

- Proposed by Dr Recebba Wilson (DataSHIELD)
- Demonstrate the relationships of the definitions to build up an understanding.
- Use this mapping to improve how the narrative around a **federated data** is communicated more coherently and logically.

Co-design with broad range of professionals

March -
May

Resource creation

Once there is more clarity on definitions and meanings. Create resources to support communication and engagement.

- Plain english Definition Tree map
- Infographics on specific concepts
- Explainer videos with well designed script and narrative

Co-produce with broad range of public members to promote access

July -
Sept

Public Engagement and reporting

Utilise the efforts made to create clarity to then engage the public more meaningfully.

- Develop a shared stimulus pack and approach to facilitation
- Deploy that across the network to get diverse perspectives
- Further engage public members not previously engaged in the data space to check understanding and findings match that of people who are less “expert lay”.
- Summarise that learning into a report to provide clear and concise public perspectives to support policy making

Involve and empower the public to influence the shape of policies and systems to promote trust

Figure 6 - Summary strategy produced following a joint meeting with the DARE UK FedRes CIG and Northern NHS SDE Network PPIE Professionals. 13

3.10. Feb 2026: Language Survey created and disseminated (ongoing)

FOCUS-5 took a leading role in developing a language survey in collaboration with the DARE UK FedRes Community Interest Group. This was part of a scoping exercise to gather structured feedback in response to a pattern of concerns clearly established in multiple forums across the health data space. The aim of this language survey is to provide evidence to concerns raised informally. This aims to improve the recognition of language-related tension across different groups operating in this space, to support the development of a jointly agreed language and tools to house and communicate agreement on terminology and expectations.

The language survey closed on the 16th April with 58 responses from a mixture of technical, governance, PPIE, public, and researchers responding from different career grades and seniorities. The responses will be analysed and shared as a point for further conversations rather than an endpoint definition. This will be used to further evidence and support the need for a common language across the federated health space.

3.11. Feb–March 2026: Prototype “Federation Atlas”

Both the DataSHIELD community and the FedRes CIG requested a searchable, web-based tool to explore language definitions related to federation concepts in the health data domain. This resulted in the initial prototyping of a web tool (Figure 7 and 8) that would visually demonstrate the interconnectedness of different parts of federated data solutions spanning both governance and technical considerations.

In March 2026, a public engagement co-design session was held to iterate and improve the tool. This is reported on separately at report: doi: [10.5281/zenodo.19368599](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19368599) [10].

Figure 7 – Graph view of terminology on an interactive website [10]

Placeholder Notice: The current definitions are placeholders and for illustration only.

Language Road Map Reset

Federated Data & Framework Analysis

Disclaimer: Prototype Content
The definitions and examples provided in this prototype are AI-generated placeholders intended for illustrative purposes only. This site is a preliminary design developed to facilitate engagement with public and professional stakeholders, who will collaboratively refine and establish the final, agreed-upon content.

Q Search nodes, tags, definitions...

Graph View Tabular View

Definition Perspective

Public Technical Researcher Governance

Framework Filters Clear Filter

Five Safes >

FAIR >

PEDRI >

SATRE >

Glossary of Terms

A structured breakdown of the federated data ecosystem.

Disclaimer: Prototype Content
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Note on Essential Characteristics: These characteristics should broadly align to framework developments such as SATRE 2.0 and represent that which is measurable or observable to determine if a criteria is met or not met.

Why - Federated Research Ecosystem

Item	Purpose	Definition (public)	Essential Characteristics	SDE Example	DARE UK Exam
A Federation <small>DEFINITION</small>	To enable secure collaborative research and analysis across multiple independent organizations without moving or compromising control of the underlying data.	A secure system where multiple organizations agree to let researchers analyze their combined data, without any of the data ever leaving its original, safe location.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Multiple independent parties: There must be more than one organisation, system, or data holder involved. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Safe People Interoperable Mutual Benefit Supporting Capabilities Local autonomy: Each party keeps its own responsibilities, decision-making, and stewardship rather than becoming part of a centrally controlled system. 	N/A	N/A

Figure 8 – Tabular view of terminology on an interactive website [10]

4. What this work revealed

The challenge is not simply that federation is technically complex. It sits at the junction of technical architecture, governance, policy, communications, and public engagement. Each group and community brings a legitimate perspective, but not always at the same level or type of definition. Technical and data groups often need language that is computationally and operationally precise, while PPIE and communications groups need concepts that stay accurate when translated into plain language and public discussion. Governance and operational stakeholders often focus on assurance, ownership, risk, and how messages may be interpreted externally. These differences create friction. The difficulty comes when this friction is not surfaced early, because definitions then drift, expectations move, and interoperability becomes harder to sustain.

Discussions among both professional and public stakeholders began to surface interconnected challenges of definition drift, operative pressures, data sovereignty expectations, and resource development. These are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1 - Summary of community issues relating to federation concepts

	Definitions Drift	Operative pressures	Data sovereignty expectations	Resource development
What surfaced	The same language was used differently across groups.	Delivery models began shaping definitions.	Some assumptions about no cross boundary sharing appeared to be shifting.	Videos and visuals progressed faster than consensus.
Risk	False assumptions of shared meaning. Impacts on interoperating.	Short term wording may not endure.	Trust can be damaged if changes are not made explicit and rationalised consistently.	Design quality masks conceptual uncertainty.
Why it matters	Weakens coherent public and professional understanding and communication.	Resources can date quickly or mislead by omission.	Public explanations must be candid about what is stable and what is evolving.	Storyboards should support learning, not imply closure too early.

4.1. Why early resource creation proved premature

This issue became visible through FOCUS-5's own practical attempts to develop explainer videos, storyboards, and infographics and their paired engagements. This challenge was also noted to be similar across our DARE UK communication colleagues, with past attempts having also struggled to overcome this context gap. With specific notes that bridging the technical and public communications in a singular solution proving difficult. These efforts were worthwhile and helped expose the communication problem, but they also showed that polished public assets can run ahead of professional consensus. That risk is particularly important in an area where assumptions appear to be shifting, including around how sovereign data remains and whether cross-boundary sharing or pooled data (physical sharing of data) approaches are becoming more normalised in some geographic regions. It was found that:

- Public materials need high-level principles that remain true even when operating models evolve.
- Stable generalisable definitions are required as an anchor for all organisations and professional groups to build out operative interpretations. If operative definitions contradict the principle of the definition, different terminology should be used to avoid confusion and potentially damage trust.
- Early concept visuals are valuable, but they should be treated as developmental tools rather than final explanations.

4.2. Why the language work became necessary

The above needs generated the impetus to gather more information in a structured fashion, moving from a collective general sense of concern to something more tangible. The aim of which is to help raise specific, actionable issues and contribute towards a solution. The survey should therefore be understood as a midpoint diagnostic exercise, not as a final statement of definition or a unilateral network position. Its role is to make visible where interpretations converge, where they differ, and which concepts require better mapping before wider public engagement can be meaningfully scaled. It can help:

- Find agreement and disagreement across stakeholder groups.
- Support a clearer definition tree or taxonomy that separates principles from examples and use cases.
- Inform later resource creation, co-design, and public deliberation with stronger shared foundations. It is not itself sufficient to define the concepts in question, which would require sustained and coordinated ongoing professional and public engagement work.

5. Implications for UK Data Research Infrastructures

The work described above suggests that communication of federation should be treated as part of the broader infrastructure of collaboration. There should be a greater emphasis on enhanced tools for communication and pushing updates across the entire sector from a singular source that is not tethered to one organisation. This would demonstrate a true representation of a federation of broader co-dependencies.

The creation of shared rules and standards often captured in operating procedures and internal documents should be moved to something more visible and widely accessible for implementation in an organisational context. Shared understanding and common mission are one of the conditions that enable effective matrix working across organisations. If definitions drift too far, expectations between groups also drift, and this can result in mixed messaging, impacting public trust. This is not because the public cannot understand complexity, but because different parts of the system appear to be describing different things. Open, layered communication is therefore more robust than oversimplified certainty. Therefore, we would propose as applicable to any data research infrastructure initiative:

- Keep technical precision and public intelligibility in active dialogue rather than separate workstreams.
- Be explicit where models differ and where assumptions are still evolving.
- Build public materials around worked examples, limitations, and use cases rather than abstract labels alone.

5.1. Recommended next steps

A more staged approach now looks sensible. The objective is not to delay communication indefinitely, but to sequence it better so that internal clarification and public explanation strengthen each other. Recommended next steps to achieve this goal include the following:

1. Continue cross-professional language work before scaling wider public campaigns.
2. Separate stable principles from current delivery choices and operational constraints.
3. Build these principles and information points into a centralised repository that becomes a “single source of truth” and supports version control that is not limited to a single organisational context.
 - a. Consider establishing a multi-agency stakeholder group with key representation to act as a steering group. Such members should be formed by those responsible for maintaining language consistency directly and report to their respective organisations proposals which their own boards can pass and challenge. Consensus should be reached across all boards or interest groups to maintain alignment and enable effective organisational-level co-creation.
4. Produce layered resources such as concise plain English summaries with worked examples for the public and drill down mechanics that increase granularity. This should include integrated technical standards such as K8TRE, RO-Crates, and SATRE 2.0, which should also be written with the minimal level of complexity required to communicate the item.
5. Recreate public-facing animations that decant the essential and principled elements of the above work and efforts into stories that build understanding, confidence, and trust in and of data-driven research and secure data environments.

6. References

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- The North West Secure Data Environment Public Advisory and Accountability Group

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9. Appendix

9.1. Library Analogy developed with the Lancashire and South Cumbria PAAG

Library or knowledge ecosystem item	Equivalent in the federated data ecosystem
A single book or diary	One person's health record or data record
Pages, chapters, and sections	Specific data fields, events, results, or parts of a record
A library	A local data holding organisation or local secure data environment
A network of libraries	A federation of organisations or data environments
Books staying on their own shelves	Data staying under local control and not being copied into one central store
The library catalogue	Metadata, common definitions, ontology, or common data model
Shared cataloguing rules across libraries	Agreed standards that allow the same query to work consistently across sites
A reader's question to the reference desk	A research query or analytic request
A request slip	An approved analytic job or protocol-driven query
The librarian	The privacy-enhancing software layer, trusted intermediary, or controlled query service
Librarian training and rules	Governance, legal controls, technical safeguards, and role based permissions
Looking only at the relevant shelf or chapter	Data minimisation and only accessing what is needed for the approved task
A supervised reading room	The secure local analysis environment
Rare books or restricted archives	Highly sensitive data requiring additional controls
The library's request register	Audit logs and traceability of queries and access
A short factual answer from each library	An approved local summary, count, or intermediate output
Combining answers from multiple libraries	Federated analytics across multiple sites
A combined summary report	Aggregated cross-site findings
Final review before releasing information	Output checking and disclosure control
Public library rules and professional standards	Assurance frameworks, compliance standards, and legal duties
A better informed reader or community	Public benefit, better knowledge, better services, and better care

9.2. Restaurant Analogy previously discussed by the North West Secure Data Environment Public Advisory and Accountability group (expanded)

Sequence	Restaurant or food ecosystem item	Equivalent in the data ecosystem
1	Diners' needs and preferences	Public need, patient need, and priority setting
2	Menu or recipe	Research question, protocol, and analysis plan
3	Approved food suppliers	Data controllers and source organisations
4	Locally sourced ingredients	Local datasets held by different organisations
5	Ingredient provenance and traceability	Data lineage, metadata, and audit trail
6	Delivery into the kitchen	Approved access into a Secure Data Environment
7	Professional kitchen	The SDE or trusted research environment as the controlled working space
8	Staff with hygiene training and defined roles	Authorised researchers, analysts, and support staff with role based access and training
9	Mise en place	Data cleaning, coding, structuring, linkage, and preparation of research-ready datasets
10	Head chef	Lead researcher or principal investigator
11	Kitchen team	Wider research team, including analysts, data managers, governance, and support staff
12	Cooking the dish	Conducting the analysis to produce findings
13	The pass or final plate check	Output checking, disclosure control, and quality assurance before release
14	Food hygiene rules, inspections, and certification	Legal, ethical, governance, and technical assurance standards
15	Front-of-house staff serving the meal	Dissemination, translation, and implementation of findings
16	Meal reaching diners	Research outputs reaching clinicians, services, policymakers, and the public
17	Nutrition, satisfaction, and feedback	Public benefit, service improvement, health gain, and impact evaluation